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SICILIAN NATURALISTIC NEWS:

8 *Muscicapa striata tyrrhenica*; 9 *Garella (Characoma) nilotica*;
10 *Mycterus curculioides*.

How to contribute

Please download from the site www.ssn.it the form (word document) and compile it
Send it in .doc format to salvatore.surdo@unipa.it

Colour photos to enrich the observation reports are welcome. When sending a photo, be sure that you have rights to publish it. Photos will have a small format, so choose it considering that the subject must be clearly visible even in this case.

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8) Mediterranean Flycatcher *Muscicapa striata tyrrhenica* Schiebel, 1910
(Aves Muscicapidae)

Source: author

Category: Unusual phenology

Number of individuals: 1

Site location: Caltabellotta (Agrigento)

Date of observation: 8.XII.2016

Records validated by: Salvatore Surdo;

Reasons of interest: The species is not reported as wintering for Sicily. This is the first record.

Reference. MASSA B., IENTILE R., ARADIS A. & SURDO S., 2021 One hundred and fifty years of ornithology in Sicily, with an unknown manuscript by Joseph Whitaker. *Biodiversity J.*, 12 (1): 27–89; <https://doi.org/10.31396/Biodiv.Jour.2021.12.1.27.89>

Angelo DITTA, via Trieste, 16 – Mazara del Vallo (TP)

Mediterranean Flycatcher *Muscicapa striata tyrrhenica*, Caltabellotta (AG), 8.XII.2016 (Photo A. Ditta)

9) *Garella (Characoma) nilotica* (Rogenhofer, 1881) (Lepidoptera Nolidae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1 (housed in collection of L. Morin)

Site location: Nature Reserve Preola Lake and Gorgi Tondi (Trapani)

Date of observation: 31.VIII.2020

Records validated by Lucio Morin

Reasons of interest: The species is not reported for Sicily. This is the first record.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaeur.org>;
<http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>

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Garella nilotica, Private collection of L. Morin, 31.VIII.2020 (Photo A. Ditta)

10) *Mycterus curculioides* Fabricius, 1781 (Coleoptera Mycteridae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1 (housed in collection of L. Morin)

Site location: Nature Reserve Preola Lake and Gorghetti Tondi (TP)

Date of observation: 31.V.2020

Records validated by Enrico Ruzzier

Reasons of interest: The species is not reported for Sicily. This is the first record.

Link di collegamento: <http://www.faunaeur.org>; <http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>

Reference: TERZANI F & CECCOLINI F., 2015. Il genere *Mycterus* Schellenberg, 1798 in Italia (Insecta Coleoptera Mycteridae). *Quad. Studi Nat. Romagna*, 41: 109-115

Mycterus curculioides Private collection of L. Morin, 31.V.2020 (leg. A. Ditta)

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